

(Table 1 contd.)

s	Piperidino	Br	H	230	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ BrN ₄ O ₄
t	Morpholino	Br	H	122-25	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ BrN ₄ O ₅
u	Diethylamino	I	H	175	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₄
v	Piperidino	I	H	222-24	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₄
w	Morpholino	I	H	145	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₅

*All compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for the bioassay and to Mr. V. N. Bhalla, Senior Technical Assistant, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for technical assistance.

References

1. A. P. BHADURI and N. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 419.
2. E. A. ISSACON and J. N. DELGADO in "Burger's Medicinal Chemistry", ed. M. E. WOITFF, 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1981, Part III, p. 836.
3. S. D. DEVEL, S. R. PEDNEKAR, S. D. SAMANT, K. D. DEODHAR and A. Y. NIMBKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 1056.
4. J. M. VIERVOND, J. LEHUEDE and M. MIOUQUE, *Eur. J. Med. Chem. Chim. Ther.*, 1983, **18**, 35.
5. L. VARGHA, E. KASZTREIMER, I. BORSY, L. FARKAS, J. KUSZMAN and P. DUMBOVICH, *Biochem Pharmacol.*, 1962, **11**, 639.
6. Hokuriku Pharmaceutical Co Ltd, Jap. Pat. 5 970 665/1984 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1984, **101**, 11051).
7. A. S. WHEELER and W. M. OATS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **32**, 770.
8. C. J. KLEMMER and J. H. HUNTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, **5**, 227.
9. L. REESE, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1887, **1**, 242.
10. P. R. DUA, "Testing Natural Products for Acute Toxicity and CNS Effects", Proceedings of UNESCO-CDRI Workshop, October 1982.

Synthesis of 4,6-Bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-aryl-pyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols as Potential Antifeedants

P. RAJANI, D. ASHOK and P. N. SARMA*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 18 April 1990, accepted 26 July 1990

PYRAZOLE and pyrazoline derivatives exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities¹. 3,4-Diaryl-1-phenylcarbamoyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines possess promising insecticidal activity². These considerations have prompted us to synthesise some 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-arylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols with a view to evaluate their antifeedant activity.

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone³ (**1**) was condensed with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of 60% aqueous KOH to yield the corresponding dichalcones (**2a-g**), which were characterised by comparison with authentic samples⁴ and through other test. The dichalcones (**2a-g**) on being

refluxed with 95% hydrazine hydrate and on usual workup of the reaction mixture gave the corresponding 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-arylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols (**3a-g**) in good yields (62-75%). As a representative case, the spectral identification of 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-phenylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinol (**3a**) has been discussed. Compound **3a** revealed ν_{max} at 3 320 (NH), 3 330-3 500br (OH) and 1 635 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 3.06 (2H, dd, $J_{4'\text{H}_B, 4'\text{H}_A}$ 18 Hz, $J_{4'\text{H}_B, 5'\text{H}}$ 5 Hz, H_B-4'), 3.47 (2H, dd, $J_{4'\text{H}_A, 4'\text{H}_B}$ 18 Hz, $J_{4'\text{H}_A, 5'\text{H}}$ 12 Hz, H_A-4'), 4.86 (2H, dd, $J_{5'\text{H}, 4'\text{H}_A}$ 12 Hz, $J_{5'\text{H}, 4'\text{H}_B}$ 5 Hz, $\text{H}-5$), 6.63 (1H, s, $\text{H}-2$) and 6.90 (1H, s, $\text{H}-5$), 7.33 (10H, m, C-5' phenyl rings) and 2.14 (br d, NH)⁵; m/z 398 (100%) consistent with its molecular formula C₂₄H₂₂O₂N₄, 397 [M-H] (32%), 321 (62%) (loss of phenyl due to α -cleavage), 294 (10%) (loss of styrene moiety), 190 (8%) (loss of two styrene moieties), 118 (pyrazoline ring cleavage) characteristic of Δ^2 -pyrazolines⁶, 310 (23%), 216 (13%), 104 (17%), 103 (5%) and 77 (12%). UV spectral data are given in Table 1.

All the compounds (**3**) were tested for their anti-feedant activity by the non-choice test method⁷ using 6 h prestarved fourth instar larvae of *Spodoptera litura*. The results are shown in Table 1. Compound **3e** exhibited highest antifeedant activity.

Experimental

Dichalcones (2a-g). *General procedure:* A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was kept at room temperature for 12 h with 60% aqueous KOH (10 ml). The product, obtained on dilution and acidification with dilute HCl was subjected to column chromatography.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3)*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	M ⁺	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm^{-1}	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) nm	Yield %	% Antifeedant activity
3a	248	398	1 635 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	225 (4.14) 274 (4.45) 330 (4.11)	75	49.6
b	247	466	1 608 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	208 (4.66) 276 (4.54) 322 (4.24)	70	90.7
c	242	466	1 610 (C=N) 3 315 (NH)	218 (4.28) 266 (4.42) 325 (4.00)	68	23.8
d	230	458	1 610 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	224 (4.56) 276 (4.61) 326 (4.30)	70	85.4
e	272	534	1 610 (C=N) 3 315 (NH)	220 (4.23) 275 (4.38) 328 (3.94)	65	94.7
f	220	518	1 610 (C=N) 3 300 (NH)	225 (4.50) 276 (4.60) 326 (4.22)	62	24.9
g	218	486	1 610 (C=N) 3 312 (NH)	203 (4.69) 270 (4.48) 330 (4.10)	67	Nil

*All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

graphy over silica gel (200 mesh). Benzene-chloroform (8 : 2, v/v) eluates on concentration afforded **2**. It gave deep red colouration with concentrated H₂SO₄ and reddish brown colouration with ethanolic FeCl₃.

4,6-Bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-aryl pyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols (**3a-g**). *General procedure*: Ethanolic solution of 2,4-bis-cinnamoylresorcinol (0.005 mol) was refluxed with 95% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) and glacial acetic acid (few drops) for 4-6 h. Ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting mixture was poured into ice-water. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1). The compounds gave blue colouration in Lassigne's test for nitrogen.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. A.V. Rama Rao; Director, I.I.C.T., Hyderabad, for recording the spectra. One of the authors (P. R.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. V. COOMBS and W. J. HOULIHAN, US Pat. 3 843 666/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **82**, 57684).
2. K. WELLINGA, A. C. GROSSCURT and R. VAN HES, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1977, **25**, 987; A. C. GROSSCURT, R. VAN HES and K. WELLINGA, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1979, **27**, 406.
3. A. S. R. ANJANEYULU, A. V. R. PRASAD and D. S. K. REDDY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, **48**, 300.
4. D. ASHOK and P. N. SARMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 900.
5. A. R. KATRITZKY in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", ed. K. T. PORTS, Pergamon, New York, 1980, Vol. 5, p. 188.

6. D. J. BLYTHIN and E. S. WAIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 583; S. HAMMERUM and P. VOLKOVY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1972, **37**, 3965; Q. N. PORTER and J. BALDAS, "Mass Spectrometry of Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1971, p. 446.
7. K. S. ASCHER and G. RONES, *International Pest Control*, 1964, March/April, 6.

Synthesis of 3-Arylidine-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1,5-benzodiazepines

(Miss) P. W. CHINCKHEDE and V. N. INGLE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 17 April 1990, accepted 26 July 1990

DIAZEPINE derivatives have a wide therapeutic activity^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised several new 3-arylidine-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1,5-benzodiazepines (**3**) (Table 1) by the condensation of 2'-hydroxy-2-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	Ar	Yield %	M p. °C
R = Phenyl			
1.	C ₆ H ₅	56	128
2.	2-Cl C ₆ H ₄	75	120
3.	3-Pyridyl	48	215
4.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	62	114
5.	2-Furyl	45	202
6.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	65	210
7.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	50	164
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	117